

Antimicrobial resistance profiles of *Escherichia coli* from dairy farms participating in an antimicrobial stewardship educational training program for farm employees.

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Supplemental Table 1. Antimicrobials included in the CMV3AGNF Antimicrobial Susceptibility Testing Plate, dilution ranges, and breakpoints for *E. coli* isolates (µg/mL) (CLSI, 2022). “S” susceptible, “I” intermediate, and “R” resistant.

Antimicrobial class	Antimicrobial drug	Dilution	Breakpoints (ug/ml)		
			S	I	R
Aminoglycosides	Gentamicin	0.25 – 16	≤4	8	≥16
	Streptomycin*	2 – 64	≤16	-	≥32
β-lactam combination agents	Amoxicillin / clavulanic acid	1/0.5 – 32/16	≤8/4	16/8	≥32/16
Cephems	Cefoxitin	0.5 – 32	≤8	16	≥32
	Ceftriaxone	0.5 – 64	≤1	2	≥4
	Ceftiofur**	0.12 – 8	≤2	4	≥8
Folate pathway antagonists	Trimethoprim/sulfamethoxazole	0.12/2.38 – 4/76	≤2/38	-	≥4/76
	Sulfisoxazole	16 – 256	≤256	-	≥512
Macrolides	Azithromycin*	0.12 – 16	≤16	-	≥32
Penicillins	Ampicillin	1 – 32	≤8	16	≥32
Phenicols	Chloramphenicol	2 – 32	≤8	16	≥32
Quinolones	Ciprofloxacin	0.015 – 4	≤0.25	0.5	≥1
	Nalidixic Acid	0.5 – 32	≤16	-	≥32
Tetracyclines	Tetracycline	4 – 32	≤4	8	≥16

*CLSI breakpoints are not established; interpretive standards used are NARMS-established breakpoints for resistance monitoring

**NARMS, 2019

Supplemental Table 2. Antimicrobial resistance profiles for *Escherichia coli* isolated from dairy farms participating in an antimicrobial stewardship educational training program for farm employees (n = 504)

AMR profile	Number of isolates
pansusceptible	312
Tet	20
Str	14
StrTet	10
Axo	8
Amp	6
Chl	6
Fox	6
AxoTet	5
StrAxoTet	5
StrChlTet	5
Sxt	5
Cip	4
StrAmp	4
StrAmpChlTet	4
AxoSxt	3
FoxAxoXnlAugAmp	3
FoxStrAxoXnlAugAmpChlTet	3
Aug	2
AxoChlTet	2
FoxAugAmp	2
GenAug	2
Nal	2
StrAmpTet	2
StrAugAmpChlTet	2
StrAxo	2
StrChlCipTet	2
AmpChlTet	1
AmpCipTet	1
AmpTet	1
AugAmp	1
AugAmpTet	1
AugChl	1
AugTet	1
AxoAmp	1

AxoAmpChlTet	1
AxoAmpTet	1
AxoAugAmpChl	1
AxoAugCip	1
AxoCipNal	1
AxoCipTet	1
AxoSxtAmpTet	1
AxoSxtChl	1
ChlTet	1
CipNal	1
FoxAugTet	1
FoxAxo	1
FoxAxoAugCip	1
FoxGenAugAmpCip	1
FoxGenNalTet	1
FoxGenStr	1
FoxNalTet	1
FoxStrAmpChlCipTet	1
FoxStrAmpNal	1
FoxStrAxoAugAmp	1
FoxStrAxoCipNalTet	1
FoxStrAxoXnlCipNalTet	1
FoxStrCip	1
FoxStrSxtAmp	1
FoxStrSxtAmpTet	1
FoxStrTet	1
FoxSxtTet	1
Gen	1
GenAmp	1
GenAxoAugCipTet	1
GenAxoChl	1
GenAxoTet	1
GenCip	1
GenStrAmpChlCip	1
GenStrAugAmpChl	1
GenStrAxoSxtTet	1
GenStrTet	1
GenSxtAmpTet	1
GenSxtChl	1
StrAmpChl	1
StrAmpNal	1

StrAug	1
StrAugAmp	1
StrAugAmpCipTet	1
StrAugAmpTet	1
StrAxoAmp	1
StrAxoAugChlCipTet	1
StrAxoSxtAugChlTet	1
StrAxoXnlAmpTet	1
StrAxoXnlSxtAugAmpChlCipTet	1
StrChlNalTet	1
StrSxtAmp	1
StrSxtChl	1
StrXnlChlTet	1
SxtAmp	1

* Fox: cefoxitin, Gen: gentamicin, Str: streptomycin, Axo: ceftriaxone, Xnl: ceftiofur, Sxt: trimethoprim/sulfamethoxazole, Fis: sulfisoxazole, Azi: azithromycin, Aug: amoxicillin/clavulanic acid 2:1 ratio, Amp: ampicillin, Chl: chloramphenicol, Cip: ciprofloxacin, Nal: nalidixic acid, Tet: tetracycline.

Supplemental Table 3. Multidrug resistance (MDR) patterns of 77 *Escherichia coli* isolated from dairy farms participating in an antimicrobial stewardship educational training program for farm employees.

MDR resistance profile*	Number of isolates
StrAxoTet	5
StrChlTet	5
StrAmpChlTet	4
FoxAxoXnlAugAmp	3
FoxStrAxoXnlAugAmpChlTet	3
AxoChlTet	2
FoxAugAmp	2
StrAmpTet	2
StrAugAmpChlTet	2
StrChlCipTet	2
AmpChlTet	1
AmpCipTet	1
AugAmpTet	1
AxoAmpChlTet	1
AxoAmpTet	1
AxoAugAmpChl	1
AxoAugCip	1
AxoCipTet	1
AxoSxtAmpTet	1
AxoSxtChl	1
FoxAugTet	1
FoxAxoAugCip	1
FoxGenAugAmpCip	1
FoxGenNalTet	1
FoxNalTet	1
FoxStrAmpChlCipTet	1
FoxStrAmpNal	1
FoxStrAxoAugAmp	1
FoxStrAxoCipNalTet	1
FoxStrAxoXnlCipNalTet	1
FoxStrCip	1
FoxStrSxtAmp	1
FoxStrSxtAmpTet	1
FoxStrTet	1
FoxSxtTet	1
GenAxoAugCipTet	1
GenAxoChl	1
GenAxoTet	1
GenStrAmpChlCip	1

GenStrAugAmpChl	1
GenStrAxoSxtTet	1
GenSxtAmpTet	1
GenSxtChl	1
StrAmpChl	1
StrAmpNal	1
StrAugAmp	1
StrAugAmpCipTet	1
StrAugAmpTet	1
StrAxoAmp	1
StrAxoAugChlCipTet	1
StrAxoSxtAugChlTet	1
StrAxoXnlAmpTet	1
StrAxoXnlSxtAugAmpChlCipTet	1
StrChlNalTet	1
StrSxtAmp	1
StrSxtChl	1
StrXnlChlTet	1

* Fox: cefoxitin, Gen: gentamicin, Str: streptomycin, Axo: ceftriaxone, Xnl: ceftiofur, Sxt: trimethoprim/sulfamethoxazole, Fis: sulfisoxazole, Azi: azithromycin, Aug: amoxicillin/clavulanic acid 2:1 ratio, Amp: ampicillin, Chl: chloramphenicol, Cip: ciprofloxacin, Nal: nalidixic acid, Tet: tetracycline.

Supplemental Table 4. Summary of the logistic regression model evaluating the effect of the training intervention on the odds ratio of AMR prevalence in *E. coli* isolates

Antimicrobial	Variable	OR	OR 95% CI		p-value
			Lower	Upper	
FOX	Farm group*Timepoint				0.035
	Control - Timepoint 1 vs Control - Timepoint 3	4.11	0.69	24.59	0.221
	Control - Timepoint 1 vs Intervention - Timepoint 1	3.39	0.77	14.92	0.177
	Control - Timepoint 1 vs Intervention - Timepoint 3	2.33	0.59	9.22	0.625
	Control - Timepoint 3 vs Intervention - Timepoint 1	0.83	0.11	5.96	1.000
	Control - Timepoint 3 vs Intervention - Timepoint 3	0.57	0.09	3.78	1.000
	Intervention - Timepoint 1 vs Intervention - Timepoint 3	0.69	0.18	2.64	1.000
STR	Farm group*Timepoint				0.057
	Control - Timepoint 1 vs Control - Timepoint 3	2.86	0.80	10.19	0.176
	Control - Timepoint 1 vs Intervention - Timepoint 1	1.57	0.38	6.51	1.000
	Control - Timepoint 1 vs Intervention - Timepoint 3	1.51	0.37	6.21	1.000
	Control - Timepoint 3 vs Intervention - Timepoint 1	0.55	0.11	2.71	1.000
	Control - Timepoint 3 vs Intervention - Timepoint 3	0.53	0.11	2.58	1.000
	Intervention - Timepoint 1 vs Intervention - Timepoint 3	0.96	0.42	2.20	1.000
AXO	Farm group*Timepoint				0.123
	Control - Timepoint 1 vs Control - Timepoint 3	2.17	0.43	10.93	1.000
	Control - Timepoint 1 vs Intervention - Timepoint 1	1.31	0.17	10.40	1.000
	Control - Timepoint 1 vs Intervention - Timepoint 3	0.93	0.12	7.16	1.000
	Control - Timepoint 3 vs Intervention - Timepoint 1	0.61	0.07	5.64	1.000
	Control - Timepoint 3 vs Intervention - Timepoint 3	0.43	0.05	3.90	1.000
	Intervention - Timepoint 1 vs Intervention - Timepoint 3	0.71	0.25	2.00	1.000
AMP	Farm group*Timepoint				0.827
	Control - Timepoint 1 vs Control - Timepoint 3	0.65	0.13	3.27	1.000
	Control - Timepoint 1 vs Intervention - Timepoint 1	0.64	0.12	3.41	1.000
	Control - Timepoint 1 vs Intervention - Timepoint 3	0.48	0.09	2.51	1.000
	Control - Timepoint 3 vs Intervention - Timepoint 1	0.99	0.21	4.68	1.000
	Control - Timepoint 3 vs Intervention - Timepoint 3	0.74	0.16	3.43	1.000
	Intervention - Timepoint 1 vs Intervention - Timepoint 3	0.76	0.27	2.08	1.000
AUG	Farm group*Timepoint				0.044
	Control - Timepoint 1 vs Control - Timepoint 3	6.43	0.35	117.57	0.540
	Control - Timepoint 1 vs Intervention - Timepoint 1	1.27	0.23	7.00	1.000
	Control - Timepoint 1 vs Intervention - Timepoint 3	0.76	0.15	3.85	1.000
	Control - Timepoint 3 vs Intervention - Timepoint 1	0.20	0.01	3.85	0.888
	Control - Timepoint 3 vs Intervention - Timepoint 3	0.12	0.01	2.19	0.318
	Intervention - Timepoint 1 vs Intervention - Timepoint 3	0.60	0.19	1.84	1.000

CHL	Farm group*Timepoint					0.742
	Control - Timepoint 1 vs Control - Timepoint 3	1.23	0.21	7.36	1.000	
	Control - Timepoint 1 vs Intervention - Timepoint 1	0.76	0.13	4.47	1.000	
	Control - Timepoint 1 vs Intervention - Timepoint 3	0.72	0.12	4.22	1.000	
	Control - Timepoint 3 vs Intervention - Timepoint 1	0.62	0.10	3.90	1.000	
	Control - Timepoint 3 vs Intervention - Timepoint 3	0.59	0.09	3.69	1.000	
	Intervention - Timepoint 1 vs Intervention - Timepoint 3	0.95	0.32	2.83	1.000	
CIP	Farm group*Timepoint					0.468
	Control - Timepoint 1 vs Control - Timepoint 3	3.04	0.13	70.58	1.000	
	Control - Timepoint 1 vs Intervention - Timepoint 1	0.74	0.07	7.48	1.000	
	Control - Timepoint 1 vs Intervention - Timepoint 3	0.88	0.09	9.18	1.000	
	Control - Timepoint 3 vs Intervention - Timepoint 1	0.24	0.01	5.81	1.000	
	Control - Timepoint 3 vs Intervention - Timepoint 3	0.29	0.01	7.07	1.000	
	Intervention - Timepoint 1 vs Intervention - Timepoint 3	1.19	0.30	4.70	1.000	
NAL	Farm group*Timepoint					0.153
	Control - Timepoint 1 vs Control - Timepoint 3	3.10	0.14	69.50	1.000	
	Control - Timepoint 1 vs Intervention - Timepoint 1	2.90	0.19	44.50	1.000	
	Control - Timepoint 1 vs Intervention - Timepoint 3	1.14	0.11	11.43	1.000	
	Control - Timepoint 3 vs Intervention - Timepoint 1	0.94	0.03	30.72	1.000	
	Control - Timepoint 3 vs Intervention - Timepoint 3	0.37	0.02	8.75	1.000	
	Intervention - Timepoint 1 vs Intervention - Timepoint 3	0.39	0.04	3.71	1.000	
TET	Farm group*Timepoint					0.482
	Control - Timepoint 1 vs Control - Timepoint 3	2.05	0.65	6.49	0.591	
	Control - Timepoint 1 vs Intervention - Timepoint 1	1.11	0.21	5.85	1.000	
	Control - Timepoint 1 vs Intervention - Timepoint 3	1.57	0.29	8.46	1.000	
	Control - Timepoint 3 vs Intervention - Timepoint 1	0.54	0.10	3.09	1.000	
	Control - Timepoint 3 vs Intervention - Timepoint 3	0.77	0.13	4.46	1.000	
	Intervention - Timepoint 1 vs Intervention - Timepoint 3	1.42	0.64	3.13	1.000	

Supplemental Table 5. Summary of the logistic regression model evaluating the effect of the training intervention on the odds ratio of MDR prevalence in *E. coli* isolates

Variable	OR	OR 95% CI		p-value
		Lower	Upper	
Farm group*Visit				0.07
Control - Timepoint 1 vs Control - Visit 3	2.53	0.50	12.73	0.77
Control - Timepoint 1 vs Intervention - Timepoint 1	0.87	0.13	5.72	1.00
Control - Timepoint 1 vs Intervention - Timepoint 3	0.61	0.09	3.92	1.00
Control - Timepoint 3 vs Intervention - Timepoint 1	0.34	0.04	2.73	1.00
Control - Timepoint 3 vs Intervention - Timepoint 3	0.24	0.03	1.87	0.39
Intervention - Timepoint 1 vs Intervention - Timepoint 3	0.70	0.28	1.75	1.00
Farm_group				0.23
Timepoint				0.41

Supplemental Table 6. Summary of the logistic regression model evaluating the effect of the state on dairy farms participating in an antimicrobial stewardship educational program for farm employees on the odds ratio of AMR prevalence in *E. coli* isolates

Antimicrobial	Variable	CA			OH				
		OR	OR 95% CI Lower	OR 95% CI Upper	p-value	OR	OR 95% CI Lower	OR 95% CI Upper	p-value
FOX	Farm group*Timepoint								
	Control - Timepoint 1 vs Control - Timepoint 3	2.20	0.29	16.58	1.00				
	Control - Timepoint 1 vs Intervention - Timepoint 1	6.45	0.49	85.22	0.33				
	Control - Timepoint 1 vs Intervention - Timepoint 3	1.73	0.23	13.07	1.00				
	Control - Timepoint 3 vs Intervention - Timepoint 1	2.93	0.18	48.45	1.00				
	Control - Timepoint 3 vs Intervention - Timepoint 3	0.79	0.08	7.85	1.00				
	Intervention - Timepoint 1 vs Intervention - Timepoint 3	0.27	0.03	2.41	0.66				
STR	Farm group*Timepoint								
	Control - Timepoint 1 vs Control - Timepoint 3	3.60	0.58	22.50	0.38	2.25	0.36	14.11	1.00
	Control - Timepoint 1 vs Intervention - Timepoint 1	2.27	0.17	31.26	1.00	1.17	0.20	6.90	1.00
	Control - Timepoint 1 vs Intervention - Timepoint 3	3.17	0.22	45.10	1.00	0.86	0.15	4.88	1.00
	Control - Timepoint 3 vs Intervention - Timepoint 1	0.63	0.04	10.82	1.00	0.52	0.07	3.88	1.00
	Control - Timepoint 3 vs Intervention - Timepoint 3	0.88	0.05	15.57	1.00	0.38	0.05	2.75	1.00
	Intervention - Timepoint 1 vs Intervention - Timepoint 3	1.39	0.38	5.16	1.00	0.73	0.24	2.24	1.00
AXO	Farm group*Timepoint								
	Control - Timepoint 1 vs Control - Timepoint 3	2.82	0.28	29.00	1.00	1.55	0.12	19.63	1.00
	Control - Timepoint 1 vs Intervention - Timepoint 1	2.35	0.08	66.27	1.00	0.70	0.04	13.64	1.00
	Control - Timepoint 1 vs Intervention - Timepoint 3	1.70	0.06	45.48	1.00	0.49	0.03	9.37	1.00
	Control - Timepoint 3 vs Intervention - Timepoint 1	0.83	0.02	29.54	1.00	0.45	0.02	10.73	1.00
	Control - Timepoint 3 vs Intervention - Timepoint 3	0.60	0.02	20.35	1.00	0.32	0.01	7.39	1.00
	Intervention - Timepoint 1 vs Intervention - Timepoint 3	0.72	0.13	4.05	1.00	0.71	0.20	2.58	1.00
AMP	Farm group*Timepoint								
	Control - Timepoint 1 vs Control - Timepoint 3	0.37	0.04	3.48	1.00	1.52	0.11	22.01	1.00

	Control - Timepoint 1 vs Intervention - Timepoint 1	0.52	0.05	5.86	1.00	0.80	0.07	9.56	1.00
	Control - Timepoint 1 vs Intervention - Timepoint 3	0.93	0.07	11.60	1.00	0.31	0.03	3.30	1.00
	Control - Timepoint 3 vs Intervention - Timepoint 1	1.41	0.18	11.36	1.00	0.53	0.04	7.88	1.00
	Control - Timepoint 3 vs Intervention - Timepoint 3	2.52	0.28	22.84	1.00	0.20	0.02	2.75	0.62
	Intervention - Timepoint 1 vs Intervention - Timepoint 3	1.79	0.35	9.04	1.00	0.39	0.09	1.60	0.45
AUG	Farm group*Timepoint								
	Control - Timepoint 1 vs Control - Timepoint 3					1.00	0.02	46.48	1.00
	Control - Timepoint 1 vs Intervention - Timepoint 1					0.37	0.01	11.10	1.00
	Control - Timepoint 1 vs Intervention - Timepoint 3					0.18	0.01	5.09	1.00
	Control - Timepoint 3 vs Intervention - Timepoint 1					0.37	0.01	11.10	1.00
	Control - Timepoint 3 vs Intervention - Timepoint 3					0.18	0.01	5.09	1.00
	Intervention - Timepoint 1 vs Intervention - Timepoint 3					0.50	0.12	2.13	1.00
CHL	Farm group*Timepoint								
	Control - Timepoint 1 vs Control - Timepoint 3	1.46	0.13	16.82	1.00	1.00	0.06	17.28	1.00
	Control - Timepoint 1 vs Intervention - Timepoint 1	1.56	0.06	44.00	1.00	0.38	0.04	3.57	1.00
	Control - Timepoint 1 vs Intervention - Timepoint 3	1.45	0.05	40.84	1.00	0.38	0.04	3.54	1.00
	Control - Timepoint 3 vs Intervention - Timepoint 1	1.07	0.03	34.07	1.00	0.38	0.04	3.57	1.00
	Control - Timepoint 3 vs Intervention - Timepoint 3	0.99	0.03	31.63	1.00	0.38	0.04	3.54	1.00
	Intervention - Timepoint 1 vs Intervention - Timepoint 3	0.93	0.14	6.17	1.00	0.99	0.25	3.99	1.00
CIP	Farm group*Timepoint								
	Control - Timepoint 1 vs Control - Timepoint 3	1.00	0.02	51.33	1.00				
	Control - Timepoint 1 vs Intervention - Timepoint 1	0.45	0.01	21.93	1.00				
	Control - Timepoint 1 vs Intervention - Timepoint 3	0.58	0.01	30.23	1.00				
	Control - Timepoint 3 vs Intervention - Timepoint 1	0.45	0.01	21.93	1.00				
	Control - Timepoint 3 vs Intervention - Timepoint 3	0.58	0.01	30.23	1.00				
	Intervention - Timepoint 1 vs Intervention - Timepoint 3	1.31	0.19	8.84	1.00				
NAL	Farm group*Timepoint								
	Control - Timepoint 1 vs Control - Timepoint 3					3.16	0.14	73.96	1.00
	Control - Timepoint 1 vs Intervention - Timepoint 1					6.35	0.26	158	0.75

Control - Timepoint 1 vs Intervention - Timepoint 3	1.53	0.17	14.13	1.00
Control - Timepoint 3 vs Intervention - Timepoint 1	2.01	0.04	98.13	1.00
Control - Timepoint 3 vs Intervention - Timepoint 3	0.49	0.02	10.96	1.00
Intervention- Timepoint 1 vs Intervention - Timepoint 3	0.24	0.01	4.97	1.00

TET

Farm group*Timepoint

Control - Timepoint 1 vs Control - Timepoint 3	3.54	0.49	25.62	0.53	1.39	0.30	6.49	1.00
Control - Timepoint 1 vs Intervention - Timepoint 1	2.12	0.09	51.85	1.00	0.73	0.12	4.43	1.00
Control - Timepoint 1 vs Intervention - Timepoint 3	2.42	0.10	59.78	1.00	1.23	0.19	7.79	1.00
Control - Timepoint 3 vs Intervention - Timepoint 1	0.60	0.02	17.81	1.00	0.53	0.08	3.39	1.00
Control - Timepoint 3 vs Intervention - Timepoint 3	0.68	0.02	20.52	1.00	0.89	0.13	5.96	1.00
Intervention- Timepoint 1 vs Intervention - Timepoint 3	1.14	0.29	4.44	1.00	1.68	0.59	4.78	1.00

Supplemental Table 7. Summary of the logistic regression model evaluating the effect of the pen on dairy farms participating in an antimicrobial stewardship educational program for farm employees on the odds ratio of AMR prevalence in *E. coli* isolates

Anti-microbial	Variable	Hospital			Fresh			Midlactation				
		OR	OR 95% CI Lower	OR 95% CI Upper	p-value	OR	OR 95% CI Lower	OR 95% CI Upper	p-value	OR	OR 95% CI Lower	OR 95% CI Upper
FOX	Control - Timepoint 1 vs Control - Timepoint 3	8.8	0.3	272	0.5	2.1	0.2	23.9	1.0			
	Control - Timepoint 1 vs Intervention - Timepoint 1	16.9	0.5	590	0.2	2.9	0.3	24.2	1.0			
	Control - Timepoint 1 vs Intervention - Timepoint 3	8.1	0.4	155	0.3	4.4	0.4	48.1	0.6			
	Control - Timepoint 3 vs Intervention - Timepoint 1	1.9	0.0	145	1.0	1.4	0.1	16.8	1.0			
	Control - Timepoint 3 vs Intervention - Timepoint 3	0.9	0.0	42.9	1.0	2.1	0.1	32.1	1.0			
	Intervention - Timepoint 1 vs Intervention - Timepoint 3	0.5	0.0	16.2	1.0	1.5	0.1	18.5	1.0			
STR	Control - Timepoint 1 vs Control - Timepoint 3	3.0	0.1	61.5	1.0	3.1	0.5	21.4	0.7	2.8	0.3	29.2
	Control - Timepoint 1 vs Intervention - Timepoint 1	1.5	0.1	35.1	1.0	1.8	0.3	10.5	1.0	1.3	0.2	8.8
	Control - Timepoint 1 vs Intervention - Timepoint 3	2.9	0.1	74.2	1.0	1.4	0.2	7.8	1.0	1.3	0.2	8.8
	Control - Timepoint 3 vs Intervention - Timepoint 1	0.5	0.0	16.3	1.0	0.6	0.1	4.4	1.0	0.5	0.0	5.2
	Control - Timepoint 3 vs Intervention - Timepoint 3	1.0	0.0	34.1	1.0	0.4	0.1	3.3	1.0	0.5	0.0	5.2
	Intervention - Timepoint 1 vs Intervention - Timepoint 3	1.9	0.2	17.4	1.0	0.8	0.2	2.7	1.0	1.0	0.2	4.2
AXO	Control - Timepoint 1 vs Control - Timepoint 3	6.3	0.2	209	0.9	1.9	0.2	23.2	1.0	1.0	0.1	16.5
	Control - Timepoint 1 vs Intervention - Timepoint 1	3.5	0.2	59.9	1.0	1.7	0.1	28.8	1.0	0.6	0.0	8.7
	Control - Timepoint 1 vs Intervention - Timepoint 3	11.6	0.3	442	0.4	2.4	0.1	44.1	1.0	0.2	0.0	2.5
	Control - Timepoint 3 vs Intervention - Timepoint 1	0.6	0.0	23.5	1.0	0.9	0.0	18.5	1.0	0.6	0.0	8.7
	Control - Timepoint 3 vs Intervention - Timepoint 3	1.8	0.0	148	1.0	1.2	0.1	28.2	1.0	0.2	0.0	2.5
	Intervention - Timepoint 1 vs Intervention - Timepoint 3	3.3	0.1	94.2	1.0	1.4	0.2	10.0	1.0	0.3	0.1	1.4
AMP	Control - Timepoint 1 vs Control - Timepoint 3	0.6	0.0	11.9	1.0	0.6	0.0	21.7	1.0	0.6	0.0	9.3
	Control - Timepoint 1 vs Intervention - Timepoint 1	1.5	0.1	32.9	1.0	0.2	0.0	5.2	1.0	0.8	0.1	9.3

	Control - Timepoint 1 vs Intervention - Timepoint 3	2.2	0.1	53.9	1.0	0.2	0.0	4.1	0.8	0.4	0.0	4.2
	Control - Timepoint 3 vs Intervention - Timepoint 1	2.5	0.1	47.1	1.0	0.4	0.0	5.4	1.0	1.2	0.1	11.0
	Control - Timepoint 3 vs Intervention - Timepoint 3	3.6	0.2	77.6	1.0	0.3	0.0	4.2	1.0	0.6	0.1	4.9
	Intervention - Timepoint 1 vs Intervention - Timepoint 3	1.5	0.1	17.2	1.0	0.8	0.2	4.0	1.0	0.5	0.1	2.8
AUG	Control - Timepoint 1 vs Control - Timepoint 3									2.1	0.1	59.0
	Control - Timepoint 1 vs Intervention - Timepoint 1									1.4	0.1	17.6
	Control - Timepoint 1 vs Intervention - Timepoint 3									0.3	0.0	2.9
	Control - Timepoint 3 vs Intervention - Timepoint 1									0.7	0.0	16.0
	Control - Timepoint 3 vs Intervention - Timepoint 3									0.2	0.0	2.9
	Intervention - Timepoint 1 vs Intervention - Timepoint 3									0.2	0.0	1.5
CHL	Control - Timepoint 1 vs Control - Timepoint 3	1.0	0.0	20.3	1.0	2.0	0.1	63.8	1.0	1.0	0.0	48.2
	Control - Timepoint 1 vs Intervention - Timepoint 1	0.7	0.0	14.9	1.0	0.8	0.1	9.2	1.0	0.8	0.0	27.6
	Control - Timepoint 1 vs Intervention - Timepoint 3	1.5	0.1	37.2	1.0	0.8	0.1	9.4	1.0	0.3	0.0	8.8
	Control - Timepoint 3 vs Intervention - Timepoint 1	0.7	0.0	14.9	1.0	0.4	0.0	8.6	1.0	0.8	0.0	27.6
	Control - Timepoint 3 vs Intervention - Timepoint 3	1.5	0.1	37.2	1.0	0.4	0.0	8.8	1.0	0.3	0.0	8.8
	Intervention - Timepoint 1 vs Intervention - Timepoint 3	2.2	0.3	17.1	1.0	1.0	0.2	6.4	1.0	0.4	0.1	2.8
TET	Control - Timepoint 1 vs Control - Timepoint 3	3.5	0.1	90.7	1.0	5.5	0.9	34.3	0.1	0.4	0.1	3.5
	Control - Timepoint 1 vs Intervention - Timepoint 1	1.6	0.1	38.0	1.0	2.5	0.4	17.3	1.0	0.3	0.0	4.0
	Control - Timepoint 1 vs Intervention - Timepoint 3	1.6	0.1	38.0	1.0	3.4	0.5	24.6	0.6	0.6	0.1	7.8
	Control - Timepoint 3 vs Intervention - Timepoint 1	0.5	0.0	16.8	1.0	0.5	0.0	4.3	1.0	0.8	0.1	7.1
	Control - Timepoint 3 vs Intervention - Timepoint 3	0.5	0.0	16.8	1.0	0.6	0.1	6.1	1.0	1.5	0.2	13.9
	Intervention - Timepoint 1 vs Intervention - Timepoint 3	1.0	0.1	7.4	1.0	1.4	0.4	4.7	1.0	1.8	0.5	6.9

Supplemental Table 8. Summary of the logistic regression model evaluating the effect of the pen on the odds ratio of AMR prevalence in *E. coli* isolates in all enrolled farms

Antimicrobial	Variable	OR	OR 95% CI		p-value
			Lower	Upper	
FOX					0.07
	Fresh vs Hospital	0.37	0.12	1.17	0.12
	Fresh vs Midlactation	1.00	0.35	2.88	1.00
	Hospital vs Midlactation	2.68	0.86	8.39	0.12
GEN					0.81
	Fresh vs Hospital	0.66	0.15	0.11	3.92
	Fresh vs Midlactation	0.74	0.25	0.19	2.87
	Hospital vs Midlactation	1.13	0.28	0.20	6.26
STR					0.02
	Fresh vs Hospital	0.86	0.37	2.03	1.00
	Fresh vs Midlactation	2.14	0.99	4.34	0.05
	Hospital vs Midlactation	2.48	1.06	6.22	0.03
AXO					0.61
	Fresh vs Hospital	0.67	0.21	2.15	1.00
	Fresh vs Midlactation	0.74	0.32	1.74	1.00
	Hospital vs Midlactation	1.10	0.36	3.40	1.00
XNL					0.14
	Fresh vs Hospital	0.25	0.04	1.79	0.27
	Fresh vs Midlactation	1.00	0.13	7.47	1.00
	Hospital vs Midlactation	0.80	0.56	27.74	0.28
AMP					0.10
	Fresh vs Hospital	0.21		0.17	1.35
	Fresh vs Midlactation	1.22	0.39	0.51	2.91
	Hospital vs Midlactation	2.54	0.77	0.88	7.32
AUG					0.06
	Fresh vs Hospital	0.30	0.08	1.08	0.07
	Fresh vs Midlactation	0.45	0.15	1.30	0.21
	Hospital vs Midlactation	1.48	0.49	4.48	1.00
CHL					<.0001
	Fresh vs Hospital	0.20	0.07	0.55	<.0001
	Fresh vs Midlactation	1.10	0.39	3.09	1.00
	Hospital vs Midlactation	5.61	1.94	16.19	<.0001

CIP					0.66
	Fresh vs Hospital	1.51	0.21	11.07	1.00
	Fresh vs Midlactation	0.76	0.24	2.44	1.00
	Hospital vs Midlactation	0.51	0.07	3.57	1.00
NAL					0.10
	Fresh vs Hospital	0.40	0.08	2.10	0.55
	Fresh vs Midlactation	2.54	0.33	19.41	0.81
	Hospital vs Midlactation	6.35	0.76	52.85	0.11
TET					0.11
	Fresh vs Hospital	0.70	0.31	1.59	0.88
	Fresh vs Midlactation	1.43	0.75	2.73	0.56
	Hospital vs Midlactation	2.04	0.88	4.74	0.13

Supplemental Figure 1. Distribution of the percentage of *E. coli* resistant isolates from the 18 participating farms to each of the evaluated antimicrobials. The boxes in violin plots show the lower, median, and upper quartiles of values, and the curves show the density of values.

Supplemental Figure 2. The proportion of resistant *E. coli* isolates to each tested antimicrobial from pooled fecal samples from control (CT) and intervention (TG) groups before (Time 1) and after (Time 2) participating in an educational program in antimicrobial stewardship in California (A) and Ohio (B). Error bars represent 95% CI.

Supplemental Figure 3. The proportion of resistant *E. coli* isolates to each tested antimicrobial from pooled fecal samples from the hospital (A), fresh (B), and mid-lactation (C) pens and from the control (CT) and intervention (TG) groups before (Time 1) and after (Time 2) participating in an educational program in antimicrobial stewardship. Error bars represent 95% CI.

